

Feedback from round 4

Question D

Do you think that the program also needs to focus on changes in support networks ? If not, please explain your arguments.

MOBILE3032 : No / If caregiver is considered one of the 'clients' then the described process will also be applicable to him/her. Any changes this person does will effect the change in the support network.

MOBILE3499 I think you cannot prescribe changes. I think you can support and be aware of impact of these changes. I think the insistence on including caregivers for all older drivers is problematic in the first instance as many would not be at a stage of having a caregiver. We also specifically noted in our research that older drivers did NOT want families involved. People with dementia and people after acquired brain injury have indicated the need for family/caregiver to be involved. It is a problem to assume that older drivers want and would accept this (and have someone taking on this role).

MOBILE8255 No, This is such an individual issue that I find it very difficult to accept that argument that we should focus on changes in support networks for everyone. I also find the assumption that this is required and/or acceptable perplexing.

Question F

Do you agree that the final goal ought to be the autonomy of the entire network in managing future changes and not the autonomy of the client alone ? If not, please explain your arguments.

MOBILE2503 : Yes, though with a focus on the individual

MOBILE6211 I think it is oversimplified to assume all future changes would not require support. I think as to whether clients or networks can manage changes would depend on the client and the nature of the change. I think the models/goals etc need to acknowledge the individual more and not be so prescriptive.

MOBILE8255 No / As per above, this is about an individual and how they choose to manage the issue and the resulting challenges. We should not dictate what this would look like.

Question H

Do you agree that the identification of the resources to implement the framework requires the implication of local and national authorities, policy makers, healthcare services, community services and social partners and thus cannot be clearly identified within this international consensus group ? If not, please explain your arguments.

MOBILE8255 The implementation of any program like this will be guided by local legislation, services and supports.

Question J

Do you agree that we should leave those commissioning the services to define further details on the modalities of their program ? If not, please explain your arguments.

MOBILE3776 : No / I believe there needs to be a "no tolerance" for drivers with dementia.

MOBILE5446 : No / I believe if the task of defining further details of the modalities of the program is left to the discretion of those commissioning the services alone, there will be limited uptake of this model. A more powerful model and report would provide a list of practical strategies, tools and techniques to inform and guide government and health policy decision-makers. Even though contexts vary infinitely, there are some general commonalities, e.g. Acute Care hospitals, Community-based Care. If tools and strategies are provided for clinicians in these general contexts, there will be a tangible starting place for advocacy. Decision-makers will be drawn to research evidence that has tangible, and practical guidelines, such as 1) directions to link loss of licensure to long-term care admission as an assessment outcome; or 2) a job description of an occupational therapist who's sole responsibility is mobility management planning (how would this therapist be funded in the public domain, what are their target outcomes, what tools would they need).

MOBILE6146 : No / those who commission services may not have understanding of clients' need; their priority is likely to focus on costing rather than quality of services

MOBILE6893 : No / If you leave the final responsibility for bringing the program to a suitable end, with defined pathways and services in place, it may never happen. in my rural setting, the delivery of health and community services is fragmented between many agencies - all under-resourced and fighting for territory. My concern is that this aspect of life will be considered almost unsolvable - bringing together transport; health; volunteers; community services and more. projects requiring this level of cooperation and teamwork rarely seem to come to fruition. Many of the people involved do not have the vision or skill level to bring forth such a massive project.

MOBILE7125 : Yes / I have ticked YES, while I do think that those commissioning the service should have the autonomy to to defining the finer detail of their programme - there should be some element of 'fidelity' to the proposed OVERALL programme and that those commissioning the service do not just focus on one aspect of the programme, they should endeavour to implement the proposed programme in its entirety.

MOBILE8255 : No / I worry about what "modalities" may be chosen. This is a sensitive issue that cannot be dealt with a check box for information delivered. I feel like people would require guidance for how to do this. I worry about this safe in the knowledge that we receive requests about a current program asking how it can be reduced to a written resource (something that is seen as manageable from a clinical perspective). The value and power of the program is lost when this occurs.

MOBILE8741 : Yes / The framework could adress the "best practice" profile of the leader of such a program, like who should be given the mandate to implement such a program.

Question L

Do you think that the current framework is complete enough to give a good basis to work on at a national level ? If not, please explain your arguments.

MOBILE5446 : 8 / I would say International Level, rather than National (which implies one country).

MOBILE6211 : 3 / I think at the moment it is overly complex without clarification of how this could work, especially in the vastly different contexts within and across nations.

MOBILE7125 : 7 / I think there may be a need to develop a 'manual' or some sort of guidance/training to enable the person themselves, carers, healthcare workers, and other stakeholders through the process of the programme. While researchers who are familiar with these issues, and healthcare professionals who have developed expertise in the area of driving assessment and driver retirement planning may consider the programme relevant and implementable, the generalist healthcare provider may not feel adequately skilled or supported to attempt to implement such a programme.

MOBILE7932 : 6 / I still query that the person/client in question has to 'accept' that they can no longer drive. I actually think they can accept that they have to use alternatives; but may never accept that they cannot return to driving per se. Hence, its reframing the approach to increasing acceptance to use alternatives to driving; particularly at that first initial stage. I think some people will never accept that they can't drive even if it is not related to their cognition; the key is to help facilitate their use of alternatives and energy; rather than focusing on their 'acceptance' - stage two you say they have to 'own' the decision of transition (to what?). I would reframe and say they own the fact they need to learn to use alternatives. As well, some of the language descriptions require refinement; obviously shaped to the jurisdiction in question and are context dependent.

MOBILE8255 4 / I have a number of concerns. Firstly, reading the feedback, i am not sure you can confidently state that consensus has been reached. There has been consistent feedback from many that has not be incorporated. I also worry that this completely misses the individual nature of this experience and that if it were to be implemented a national level, we would see people being forced to own a decision (when in reality for some people that will never happen), the first step will be to encourage them to move or change occupations (rather than seeking to advocate for services and support where they are and help them develop ways to engage in their occupations with the new status as a non-driver). I would be really quite dissatisfied if this was the outcome of this "consensus" study and really worry that this could occur.

Question P

Do you have any further critics or comments ?

MOBILE3032 : 1st impression of Fig 1 is overwhelming - perhaps simplify it better or break into 2 figures?

MOBILE3499 : I think the diagrams and figures should be central in the report and not in an appendices

MOBILE3618 : The Round 4 report reads really well. However I find Fig 1 on page 9 really difficult to read - there just seems to be too much happening and too many abbreviations and keys. It would be great to be kept informed of any role out of a 'Mobility Management Program' in Switzerland and if this consensus study is going to be presented.

MOBILE5446 The process was very informative to understand the theoretical approach other clinicians and health professionals are taking. However, this approach remains in an "ideal world" that seems would be only as successful as the larger public shares the same sentiments as the clinicians and health professionals.

A bigger issue is the cultural shift and change in perceptions to allow this model to be embraced. It comes down to changing the perception (as mentioned in the report) that driving is a privilege, not a right - which is not well appreciated across the developed countries.

MOBILE6146 : No

MOBILE6211 : I am not sure comments from previous rounds have been addressed in moving forward to this stage. I think existing interventions that use this kind of approach should be explicitly acknowledged (eg UQDRIVE program). I think it is problematic to assume older people have a cognitive impairment and have a caregiver involved. The use of 'patient' throughout the document suggests that the community, person centred focus is not being followed. While you acknowledge 'stages' can be simultaneously worked on, i am not sure the current model supports this. I also think some endpoints are not realistic for all individuals. For example, it is entirely possible for someone to be engaged in their meaningful occupations within the community without ever accepting that they needed to stop driving. Sometimes getting engaged/using alternatives drives this acceptance if it comes - where the model has that occurring later. I think it is problematic to indicate this model fits all settings (p3) - I don't believe it does. As previously mentioned, the assumption of caregivers and cognitive impairment is also problematic and also likely to alienate the group you are aiming to work with.

MOBILE6893 : Thank you for the opportunity to contribute

MOBILE7125 : I am not sure what the purpose of another round might be. I do think there may be a need for the development of a 'user guide' to make the programme more readily translatable into practice. Non-specialist health care practitioners, older drivers and their carers may need more concrete guidance to engage with the programme.

MOBILE7564 : Great experience - helpful to also read others comments.

MOBILE7932 : Not sure I understand the above question.

MOBILE8255 : To be honest, I do not know how to answer this as I do not feel like feedback has been listened to with previous rounds... I do apologise but I do not feel like consensus has been reached and I find it difficult to endorse such a prescriptive process with named end-points, etc. What happened to individualised goal setting that would set the end-points?